

Table 1. Estimates of genetic parameters for reproductive stage salinity tolerance score and K concentration and Na-K ratio in shoots of 6 × 6 diallel.

Genetic parameter	Estimate ± SE					
	Salinity tolerance score		K		Na-K	
D	10.760* ^a	± 1.080	0.056*	± 0.009	0.099*	± 0.017
H ₁	7.532*	± 2.916	0.067*	± 0.024	0.129*	± 0.044
H ₂	5.536*	± 2.645	0.056*	± 0.022	0.092*	± 0.039
h ²	3.299	± 1.786	0.075*	± 0.015	0.030	± 0.027
F	6.663*	± 2.698	0.004	± 0.023	0.096*	± 0.043
E	0.290	± 0.441	0.012*	± 0.004	0.006	± 0.007
Proportional values						
(H ₁ /D) ^{1/2}	0.837		1.091		1.139	
H ₂ /4H ₁	0.184		0.210		0.178	
[(4DH ₁) ^{1/2} + F]/ [(4DH ₁) ^{1/2} - F]	2.175		1.062		2.484	
r (Wr + Vr)/Yr	0.96		0.60		0.971	
h ₂ /H ₂	0.596		1.326		0.324	
h ² (narrow sense)	0.65		0.55		0.410	

^a * = significant at the 5% level.

than dominant genes in the tolerant varieties CSR10 and CSRI for salinity tolerance score at the reproductive phase and K⁺ uptake while dominant alleles were more concentrated than recessive in Nona Bokra, CSR10, and CSRI in that order. Wr-Vr graphic analysis suggested the involvement of both major and minor genes for all the traits investigated.

Combining ability analysis by Griffing's method confirmed the significance of both additive and nonadditive effects, with additive effects showing greater importance in the inheritance of the traits (Table 2). The

varieties CSR10 and CSRI were good general combiners for all three traits examined and could be useful in rice breeding programs aiming to improve salt tolerance. High heterotic effects found in some crosses suggest the potential of hybrid rice for salt-affected soils. CSR10 is now being used as a donor in an India-IRRI collaborative project on salinity tolerance and also as a low-cost biological amendment for managing salt-affected soils in India.

Table 2. Combining ability analysis for salinity tolerance score at reproductive stage and K concentration and Na-K ratio in shoots of 6 × 6 diallel.

Source	df	Mean square		
		Salinity tolerance score at reproductive stage	K	Na-K ratio
gca	5	15.36** ^a	0.238**	0.100**
sca	15	3.71**	0.065**	0.033**
Error	40	0.22	0.012	0.006
gca/sca		4.14	3.66	3.03

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

Cited references

- Griffing B. 1956. Concept of general and specific combining ability in relation to diallel crossing systems. *Aust. J. Biol. Sci.* 9:463-493.
- Hayman B. 1954. The theory and analysis of diallel crosses. *Genetics* 39:789-809.
- Mishra B. 1991. Combining ability and heterosis for yield and yield components related to reproductive-stage salinity and sodicity tolerance in rice *Oryza sativa* L. In: *Rice genetics II*. Manila, (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 761.
- Mishra B. 1994. Breeding for salt tolerance in crops. Pages 226-259 In: Rao et al, editors. *Salinity management for sustainable agriculture—25 years of research at CSSRI*. Karnal, (India): Central Soil Salinity Research Institute. ■

Stress tolerance

Epigenetic control of tolerance for transient low light stress in rice

Y. F. Chen, Institute of Agrobiological Genetics and Physiology, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China; C. G. Li, Institute of Food Crops, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China

Rice has smaller photosynthetic capacity and less accumulation of assimilates—resulting in a low yield—under low light stress than does rice grown under adequate solar radiation. For example, rice yield during the wet season is 65.2% of that

during the dry season (Murty and Sahu, 1987), and rice that receives half of the full sunshine has 57% less yield than rice receiving full sunshine (Murty 1992). Tolerance for low light stress is genetically controlled, but until recently little has been known about the genes involved. To explore whether cytoplasmic genes are involved in controlling this physiological character, we used several sets of reciprocal cross combinations in which double parents show typical tolerance for or sensitivity to transient low light stress.

Detached flag leaves at the heading stage were inserted into tap water and equilibrated under near saturated light intensity (500 μE m⁻²s⁻¹). For a different set of leaves, light intensity was rapidly decreased to 110 μE m⁻²s⁻¹ and leaves were

incubated for 1 min under low irradiation. At the same time, net photosynthesis rates (Pn, μmol CO₂ m⁻²s⁻¹) in two light environments (expressed as Pn 500 and Pn 110) were determined with a LI-6200 photosynthesis system. To indicate the degree of Pn decrease immediately after irradiation, we used (Pn 500-Pn 110)/Pn 500. The threshold was determined to be half of the decrease of Pn(max) at 110 μE m⁻²s⁻¹. The leaves were tolerant when their Pn changes were below the threshold or sensitive when Pn changes were over the threshold under transient light stress. Data in the table were averages of 3-6 repetitions.

Eight sets of combination among the 11 parents (see table) were classified into three kinds according to the degree of Pn reduction of the parents: 1) both parents have a

Changes in net photosynthetic rate (Pn) in flag leaves of reciprocal-cross F₁ and their parents under transient low light impact.

Combination number	(Pn 500-Pn 110)/Pn 500			
	Parent 1	Parent 2	F ₁	
			Parent 1/Parent 2	Parent 2/Parent 1
1	LH422 (I) ^a	Pal (I)	0.747 ± 0.1741	0.326 ± 0.0874
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.518 ± 0.0339		
2	YS8072 (J) ^b	Xiushui 04 (J)	0.776 ± 0.1237	0.396 ± 0.1266
	0.625 ± 0.0304	0.435 ± 0.0641		
3	Sunong 30367 (I)	02428 (J)	0.891 ± 0.0707	0.430Li ± 0.0848
	0.834 ± 0.0767	0.482 ± 0.0283		
4	LH422 (I)	Minghui 75 (I)	0.702 ± 0.1524	0.396 ± 0.0820
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.356 ± 0.0601		
5	Luweidao (I)	Zhongguo 91 (J)	0.621 ± 0.0099	0.473 ± 0.0233
	0.702 ± 0.0693	0.361 ± 0.1277		
6	LH422 (I)	029 (J)	0.693 ± 0.0127	0.527 ± 0.0636
	0.716 ± 0.1446	0.448 ± 0.1916		
7	YS8072 (J)	Luweidao (I)	0.793 ± 0.1392	1.09 ± 0.153
	0.625 ± 0.0304	0.702 ± 0.0693		
8	02428 (J)	IET9702 (I)	0.477 ± 0.1209	0.446 ± 0.1044
	0.482 ± 0.0283	0.439 ± 0.0523		

^aI = indica subspecies. ^bJ = japonica subspecies.

small reduction in Pn, such as combination 8; 2) Pn reduction in both parents is large (such as combination 7); and 3) one parent has a large reduction in Pn and the other has a small reduction (combination 1). In the third kind of combination, performances of Pn reduction in the reciprocal cross F₁ are basically identical to those in corresponding maternal lines under low irradiation impact. Results in the other combinations also support this.

It can therefore be concluded that genes related to tolerance for transient low light stress in rice are mainly located in the cytoplasm. However, in some situations nuclear genes from both maternal and paternal lines interact with cytoplasmic genes from the maternal line to make tolerance stronger (in combination 1) or weaker (in combination 7). The large and positive correlations between Pn and accumulation of dry matter will make this genetic behavior of shared tolerance in rice useful in breeding for high yield. ■

Stress tolerance—other structures

Screening somaclonal variants with tolerance for both shade and photooxidation in rice

Y. F. Chen and L. H. Sun, Institute of Agrobiological Genetics and Physiology, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China

Rice plants must have increased adaptation to light stresses, including shade and photooxidation, before higher photosynthesis and yield can be achieved. Somaclonal variation is a new source of tolerance for shade and photooxidation. We have obtained some somaclonal variants with tolerance for both shade and photooxidation (double tolerance) in rice.

Calli were induced on solid N6 medium with 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ liter from mature

caryopses of three varieties, 02428, Zhongguo 91, and 842 to both shade and photooxidation, and then subcultured on the same medium. Calli were transferred on to solid MS medium with 2 mg BA L⁻¹ + 0.25 mg NAAL⁻¹ + 0.25 mg IAA L⁻¹ to regenerate plants (R₁). Posterities of R₁ were sexually reproduced.

Somaclonal variants from different parents were identified under shade and photooxidative conditions. Rice plants were grown from booting to grain tilling (3 wk) under two layers of light gray plastic nets, which allowed about 30% natural sunlight to penetrate. Under shade, specific leaf weight declined, with less than 20% of the varieties being classified as tolerant. The upper 2d leaves were gathered at booting stage and submerged in tap water containing low CO₂ and low O₂. They were

Differential responses of rice somaclonal variants under shading and photooxidative conditions.

Somaclonal variant	Grade of photooxidation ^a	Decline of SLW (%) ^b
02428 (parent)	I	4.2
02428hong (R ₅)	II	13.4
02428h (R ₅)	I	5.3
Zhongguo 91 (parent)	I	21.3
CX-1 (R ₄)	I	14.7
842 (parent)	V	25.9
842241-1 (R ₂)	IV	19.2
842241-2 (R ₂)	III	- ^c
842houshi (R ₂)	II	31.7
84202-chou 1 (R ₂)	IV	-
84202-chou 7 (R ₂)	II	-
84202-chou 9 (R ₂)	IV	24.9
84202-chou 10 (R ₂)	II	18.6

^aI = whole leaf area green, II = only leaf tip yellow, III = 1/3 of leaf area yellow, IV = 1/2 of leaf area yellow, V = 3/4 of leaf area or whole leaf area yellow. Upper 2nd leaves from the main stems were used, replicated three times. ^bSLW = specific leaf weight. The uppermost leaves from the main stems were used, except CX-1. ^c- = not determined.